

Spectroscopic Studies on some New Azo Dyes derived from 4-Methylesculetin and their Biological Activity

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Manuscript received 18 June 1996, accepted 4 December 1996

Some new mono azo dyes derived from 6,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin have been prepared and their electronic absorption spectra have been investigated in organic solvents of varying polarities. The spectra, in ethanol, display mainly five absorption bands which are assigned to their appropriate electronic transitions. The effect of substituents on the absorption spectra have been investigated. The important ir bands and ¹H nmr signals are assigned and discussed in relation to molecular structure. The presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding and quinone-hydrazone tautomerism within the molecules have been demonstrated from the ir spectra. The biological activities of the azo compounds towards some filamentous microscopic fungi, yeasts and bacteria have also been studied.

The absorption spectra of azobenzenes and their derivatives have been the subject of many investigations^{1,3}. The studies revealed that the electronic absorption spectra are affected considerably by changes in the nature, position and number of substituents.

4-Methylesculetin (6,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin) is of great importance as a good organic chelating agent and chromophoric indicator². In the present study, new azo dyes based on 6,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (expected to have a good ligating character and biological activity) have been prepared. The electronic absorption spectra have been assigned and correlated to their molecular structure. The ir spectra of the solid compounds, ¹H nmr spectra as well as their biological activity have been discussed in terms of molecular structure.

(1-11)

X = H (1), *o*-OH (2), *o*-COOH (3), *o*-NO₂ (4), *o*-OCH₃ (5), *o*-AsO(OH)₂ (6), *p*-OH (7), *p*-COOH (8), *p*-Cl (9), *p*-Br (10), *p*-CH₃ (11)

Results and Discussion

The purity of the compounds (1-11) was confirmed by m.p. Their elemental analyses (1-11) showed a satisfactory agreement with the expected tentative formulae.

Electronic absorption spectra in ethanol and cyclohexane : The spectra of the azo compounds under investigation were recorded in ethanol (polar) and cyclohexane (non-polar) solvents in the range 190–550 nm. In ethanol, the spectra display mainly five bands; the first two bands (A and B), found in the range 205–242 nm are assigned to the medium and low energy π - π^* transitions within the aromatic moieties representing the (¹La \rightarrow ¹A) and (¹Lb \rightarrow ¹A) states, respectively. This is confirmed by the high values of molar extinction coefficient (ϵ , dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) amounting to 3.14×10^4 – 4.00×10^5 (Table 2). The third band (C) appearing at $\lambda \approx 295$ nm in the spectra of all compounds, is due to the n - π^* transition of the C=O and/or the N=N group². The fourth band (D) located at longer wavelength side (310–350 nm), being sensitive to both solvent polarity and nature of substituent, can be assigned to π - π^* transition within the azo group involving charge transfer (CT) interactions through the whole molecule represented as :

It is worthy to mention that, the relatively shorter wavelength at which the CT band takes place is expected due to the formation of an intramolecular hydrogen bond between the two adjacent hydroxyl groups in the coumarin moiety

forming a stable five-membered ring, thus inhibiting the hydroxyazo \rightleftharpoons quinonehydrazone tautomerism. The appearance of the fifth band (E) only in the spectra of the compounds having a strong withdrawing groups in *ortho*- and *para*-positions with respect to N=N group (compounds 4, 8, 10). This band is attributed to the hydrazone form of the compounds present as new species.

Solvent effect : The absorption spectra of the compounds were scanned in different solvents of varying polarities (representative example is given in Fig. 1). Though bands due to the local π - π^* transitions in the uv-region display an irregular solvent shift, yet the general trend is a red-shift with increased solvent polarity. This behaviour is characteristic of the π - π^* transition of the substituted benzenes where the solvent-substituent interaction would be additive or counteracts the solvent shift of the aromatic nucleus¹. On the other hand, the longer wavelength band corresponding to the intramolecular CT interaction displays some shifts in all solvents studied.

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of compound 1 in different organic solvents (1) acetone, (2) dioxane, (3) methanol, (4) CCl_4 , (5) CHCl_3 , (6) propanol, (7) butanol, (8) benzene and (9) DMF.

To assess the influence of solvents on the CT band, the so-called macroscopic and microscopic solvent polarity parameters were applied. The plots of $\Delta\nu$ (cm^{-1}) vs $(D-1)/(D+1)^2$ and λ_{max} (nm) vs $f(D)$, $\phi(D)^6$, π , α , β^+ , E_T and $Z^{8,9}$ values gave nonlinear relations. This indicates that none of such parameters solely is the predominating factor affecting the position of the CT band, but the contribution of specific solute-solvent interaction (solvation or more effectively hydrogen-bonding between solute and solvent molecules) also takes place. So, the shift on the CT band position is actually the result of changed solvent polarity and the shift due to intermolecular hydrogen bond.

Substituent effect : The position of the CT-band may depend on the nature of the substituent attached to the phenyl group. In this case, the position of the CT-band should obey the Hammett linear free energy relationship,

$$\lambda_X = \lambda_H + \rho \sigma_X^*$$

The plot of λ_{max} of the CT-bands against Hammett substituent constant (σ^*) gives a straight-line, with a value of ρ amounting to 33.3, indicating that the CT-band is directly affected by the nature of substituent (X). The apparently high value of ρ denotes strong conjugation in the molecule, hence a structure that would approach a planar form.

Ir spectra : The assignment of the ir absorption bands was carried out by a method similar to that suggested by Looker¹⁰.

The broad band appearing at 3420 – 3319 cm^{-1} in all the compounds corresponds to the stretching vibrations of OH and CH groups. Two bands at 3150 – 2900 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the asym and sym stretching vibration of the CH groups. This was recognised by Coblenz¹¹ and Bonino¹² pointing out that the characteristic C–H bands of aromatic and aliphatic compounds occur at different recognisable positions in this region. The weak band at 3084 – 3277 cm^{-1} range, found in the spectra of compounds 1–10 is due to the stretching vibration of the NH group resulting from the formation of the quinone-hydrazone tautomer. All compounds show a band at ≈ 2932 cm^{-1} due to the stretching vibration of CH_3 group.

The bands at 1714 – 1670 and 1620 – 1600 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the stretching vibration of the C=O and the C=C ring absorption bands, respectively. The bands at 1465 – 1401 and 1346 – 1257 cm^{-1} are characteristic for the stretching vibration of the N=N and OH in-plane deformation.

Most of the strong bands appearing in the range 1000 – 625 cm^{-1} , are due to the out-of-plane deformation vibration of the hydrogen atoms present in the ring. The band position can be discussed in terms of the number of adjacent hydrogen atoms. The weak to medium bands at 858 – 824 cm^{-1} for compounds 6–11 are assigned to the out-of-

plane C–H deformation vibration of two adjacent hydrogen atoms, while those at 863–746 cm^{-1} for compounds 2–6 are due to the deformation vibration of four adjacent hydrogen atoms. In the spectrum of compound 1, the strong band at 753 cm^{-1} is due to the deformation vibration of 5 adjacent hydrogen atoms.

¹H nmr spectra : The spectra of all compounds show a singlet nmr signal in the range δ 2.25–2.50 due to the three protons of the methyl group, δ 6.00 \pm 0.2 (removed on deuteration) due to the two protons of the hydroxyl groups. The signals at δ 6.30 and 8.05 in the spectra of compounds 3 and 8 are due to the protons of COOH group present in *ortho*- and *para*-positions to the azo linkage, respectively. While those at δ 3.65 and 2.55 are due to the protons of OCH₃ and CH₃ groups in compounds 5 and 11 respectively. The broad signal appearing in the range δ 8.40–9.70 is due to the NH proton resulting from the quinonoid structure supporting the quinone-hydrazone \rightleftharpoons hydroxyazo tautomerism. Multiple signals of the aromatic protons appear in the range δ 6.65–7.80.

TABLE I—ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION BANDS OF THE 4-METHYLESCULETIN AZO COMPOUNDS IN ETHANOL*

Compd.	Band A	Band B	Band C	Band D	Band E
	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\epsilon_{\text{max}}^{(1)}$	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\epsilon_{\text{max}}^{(1)}$	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\epsilon_{\text{max}}^{(2)}$	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\epsilon_{\text{max}}^{(2)}$	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\epsilon_{\text{max}}^{(2)}$
1	210 (0.31)	225 (1.05)	285 (0.99)	335 (0.81)	–
2	208 (2.25)	218 (2.15)	286 (1.05)	340 (1.14)	–
3	208 (2.21)	212 (0.85)	288 (1.08)	335 (1.40)	–
4	205 (0.64)	215 (0.32)	295 (0.99)	360 (1.50)	402 (0.73)
5	208 (4.01)	242 (2.46)	290 (0.92)	343 (1.82)	–
7	211 (0.35)	240 (0.62)	295 (1.13)	345 (1.30)	–
8	205 (0.79)	233 (0.35)	292 (1.17)	340 (1.65)	392 (0.84)
9	210 (2.12)	228 (2.06)	295 (0.90)	362 (1.56)	410 (0.80)
10	205 (0.79)	215 (0.36)	290 (1.50)	343 (2.67)	408 (0.75)
11	205 (2.27)	230 (1.92)	288 (0.75)	340 (1.31)	–

* λ_{max} (nm); ϵ_{max} ($\text{dm}^3 \text{cm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) $\times 10^5$ (1) and $\times 10^4$ (2).

Antimicrobial activities : The effect of the azo compounds was investigated against filamentous microscopic fungi, yeasts and bacteria : *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium cyclopium*, *Botrytrichum*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Rhizopus oryzae*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus*

subtilis. The azo compounds were added directly to the cultivation media and their influence on the growth of microorganisms was considered. The multiplication of culture (for yeast and bacteria) in the presence of the azo compounds was studied by measuring turbidity using photo colorimeter. From the values obtained, the curves of growth were designed and from these, values of ID 50 an ID100 were graphically evaluated¹³. For the antifungal test, Czapek-Dox's nutrient solution (20 ml) after the addition of tested substances was inoculated by the fungus spores and mycelium homogenate. The values of minimum inhibition concentration (MIC) were determined. The substances were tested in concentrations 8, 40, 200 and 1000 mmol.

The results indicate that compounds 2 and 7 (containing *o*- and *p*-OH groups) inhibit the growth of the fungi more intensively (MIC 200–850 ppm), whereas other compounds are ineffective even when present in higher concentration.

Experimental

The monoazo dyes were prepared by coupling of 6,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (in sodium acetate) with the diazonium salts of the corresponding aniline derivatives. 6,7-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was synthesised as previously recommended¹⁴. The azo compounds were purified by crystallisation from acetic acid-water (30%, v/v acetic acid) : 1, m.p. 233–35°; 2, 200–03°; 3, 256–60°; 4, 188–90°; 5, 245–47°; 6, 263–65°; 7, 253–54°; 8, 203–05°; 9, 236–38°; 10, 228–30°; 11, 145–48°; all compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses (Microanalytical Center, Cairo University).

Solutions of the dyes (10^{-3} M) were prepared in the appropriate volume of pure solvent. Solutions for spectral measurements were obtained by appropriate dilution of the stock ones.

Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer λ 3B spectrophotometer using 10 mm matched silica cells, ir spectra (KBr) on a Beckmann IR 4220 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. M. R. Metwally, Department of Botany, Benha University, for biological data.

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